

THE ROLE OF ANDRAGOGICAL APPROACH TO TEACHING ENGLISH TO ENGINEERS AND TECHNICIANS

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In the Era of Revival of the New Epoch of the Powerful State under the visionary and effective leadership of our Esteemed President, education, science, innovation and production systems are being developed and their connection is constantly being strengthened in a coordinated manner with the participation of young generation. Declaring 2023 as the year of “Happy Youth with Arkadag Serdar” is also a clear evidence of the great attention paid to the young generation in our country. For this reason training of high-level young specialists, by using their intellectual level, talent, skills, knowledge, science, culture and other abilities properly and fully is one of the primary tasks of instructors and teachers in higher educational institutions.

In accordance with the language policy, the National Programs and Concepts that have been adopted recently in our country, English is one of the main foreign languages to be studied at all educational institutions. Therefore, improving the proficiency of English has become the major requirement for high quality education [1]. It is especially true for Oguz han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan since English is medium of instructions as well as an essential tool for communication at university. The students of this higher educational institution are expected to become competent specialists, who are able to raise their qualification using materials in foreign language and communicating with their colleagues from abroad.

In this perspective, to promote English language teaching the instructor has to choose proper methods and approaches so he/she can address to the educational needs of the engineering students. Traditionally, there are two types of teaching approaches. These are andragogy and pedagogy approaches. The word andragogy stems from the Greek word andragogos which means “teaching adults.” Andragogy is defined as the art and science of helping adults to learn by Knowles [2], while pedagogy is used for young learners. Seen from their age, students at university are categorized into adult learners. Therefore, this paper aims to share experience in the implementation of andragogical approach to teaching ESP at Oguz han Engineering and Technology University of Turkmenistan.

Although the early concepts on adult education go back to the early 1800s, the concept and name “andragogy” was popularized by Malcom Knowles to distinguish adult education from pedagogy or child education. Knowles [2] initially based his andragogical model on four pillars: (a) student’s self-directed learning; (b) students’ accumulated and growing experience for learning; (c) students’ readiness to learn; (d) shift from subject-centered to performance-centered.

The concept of self-directed learning is a form of study in which students have a primary responsibility for planning, carrying out and conducting their own learning activities. By taking control of their own learning activities students are able to develop self-esteem and self-confidence. In this approach the teacher acts as the facilitator who considers learners as capable of self-direction and self-development [3]. Students are also able to assess their needs and focus on relevant skills which they have to improve.

With regard to the concept of students' accumulated and growing experience for learning in which they are treated as someone who already has prior knowledge, will help them to use their knowledge and experience in context with the real-world problems that they will have to solve. This assumption relies on the idea that adults have more experiences than children to apply information or draw from it. Thus, effective learning will draw upon these experiences. It also focuses on motivation of students to become lifelong learners.

Based on the assumption of readiness to learn, students improve their language skills through a field that is already known and relevant to them. This means that they can use what they learn in the ESP classes right away in their work and studies [4]. It also enables them to use the language they know to learn even more, since their interest in their field or major will motivate them to interact with various scopes of learning materials.

While subject-centered ESP class focuses on the content of the curriculum, performance-centered approach focuses on the students' participation. They are able to design, manage, and lead their own learning styles based on personal needs and interests. This approach also enhances problem-solving skill and critical thinking in students which can be result in boosting student engagement, accelerating learning and improving content retention.

Taking into consideration above mentioned, it can be concluded that andragogical approach builds interactive learning atmosphere for the adult learner, especially in teaching ESP. When ESP classes are conducted in this approach they must provide practical exercises, project works, role-plays, case studies, addressing specific real-world problems. Effective use of group discussions and group work is essential. Technical vocabulary can be taught and revised using crosswords, word searches and puzzles, and communication activities can take the form of games. In adult learning situations, teaching can focus more on training. Training activities can be less formal, and the role of andragogical approach is to move away from the theoretical knowledge and into a practical application of the knowledge.

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